

Traditional and Complementary Medicine (TCM) in Health Tourism: Comparative Policy and Practice Analysis of Türkiye and Mexico*

Geleneksel ve Tamamlayıcı Tıp Yöntemlerine Dayalı Sağlık Turizmi: Türkiye ve Meksika Karşılaştırması

Research Article/Araştırma Makalesi

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Abstract

In the health tourism literature, comparative country analyses focusing on Traditional and Complementary Medicine (TCM) practices remain scarce, constituting a significant research gap. This study aims to examine TCM-based health tourism in the cases of Türkiye and Mexico. The analysis covers five dimensions: (i) regulatory framework, (ii) supply structure and service provision, (iii) demand dynamics and statistical indicators, (iv) quality and safety, and (v) ethical and societal implications. Data were obtained from official statistics and institutional reports (USHAŞ, TÜİK; Secretaría de Salud, COFEPRIS), the World Health Organization's framework on traditional medicine, and selected academic publications. The findings reveal that in Türkiye, TCM practices have been institutionalized through the 2014 regulation, with international patient arrivals reaching 1,506,442 and revenues amounting to USD 3.02 billion in 2024; in the first two quarters of 2025 733,798 visitors and USD 1.62 billion in revenues were recorded. In Mexico, indigenous healing practices (temazcal, herbolaria, curanderismo) coexist with cross-border demand for dental and medical tourism, with industry reports estimating approximately 1.2–3 million health-related visitors annually, predominantly originating from the United States. Türkiye demonstrates comparative advantages in regulatory clarity, institutional governance, and integration with thermal tourism, whereas Mexico exhibits strengths in cultural authenticity, geographic proximity, and cost competitiveness. Policy recommendations emphasize strengthening safety and quality standards, expanding accreditation processes, diversifying service offerings, and institutionalizing ethical considerations. This study fills a gap in the health tourism literature by providing a comparative analysis of TCM-oriented practices in Türkiye and Mexico.

Özet

Sağlık turizmi literatüründe geleneksel ve tamamlayıcı tıp (Traditional and Complementary Medicine, TCM) uygulamalarına yönelik karşılaştırmalı ülke analizlerinin sınırlı olması önemli bir araştırma boşluğudur. Bu çalışma, Türkiye ve Meksika örnekleri üzerinden TCM'e dayalı sağlık turizmini incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Çalışmada, (i) düzenleyici çerçeve, (ii) arz yapısı ve hizmet sunumu, (iii) talep dinamikleri ve sayısal göstergeler, (iv) kalite ve güvenlik, (v) etik ve toplumsal etkiler boyutları temel alınarak iki ülke karşılaştırılmıştır. Veriler, resmi istatistikler ve kurumsal raporlar (USHAŞ, TÜİK; Secretaría de Salud, COFEPRIS), Dünya Sağlık Örgütü'nün geleneksel tıp çerçevesi ve seçilmiş akademik yayınlardan derlenmiştir. Bulgular, Türkiye'de TCM uygulamalarının 2014 tarihli yönetmelikle kurumsallaştığını, 2024'te uluslararası sağlık hizmeti alan ziyaretçi sayısının 1.506.442'ye, gelirin 3,02 milyar ABD dolarına ulaştığını; 2025'in ilk iki çeyreğinde ise 733.798 ziyaretçi ve 1,62 milyar ABD doları gelir kaydedildiğini göstermektedir. Meksika'da ise yerli şifa pratikleri (temazcal, herbolaria, curanderismo) ile sınır-ışan dış/medikal turizm birlikte varlık göstermekte olup, literatür ve sektör analizleri ülkeye yılda yaklaşık 1,2–3 milyon sağlık amaçlı ziyaretçi geldiğini ve akışın büyük ölçüde ABD kaynaklı olduğunu bildirmektedir. Türkiye düzenleyici netlik, kurumsal yönetim ve termal turizm entegrasyonu ile öne çıkarken; Meksika kültürel otantiklik, sınır yakınlığı ve maliyet avantajıyla farklı bir rekabet üstünlüğü sergilemektedir. Sonuç olarak, politika önerileri güvenlik ve kalite standartlarının güçlendirilmesi, akreditasyon süreçlerinin yaygınlaştırılması, ürün çeşitlendirmesi ve etik hassasiyetlerin kurumsallaştırılması yönünde şekillenmiştir. Bu çalışma, sağlık turizmi literatüründe TCM odaklı Türkiye–Meksika karşılaştırması eksikliğini gidererek özgün bir katkı sunmaktadır.

Introduction

Health tourism encompasses the travel of individuals abroad for preventive, therapeutic, rehabilitative, and health-enhancing services (Ministry of Health, 2024). Within this umbrella, subcategories such as medical tourism, thermal tourism, and tourism for the elderly and disabled exist. This article specifically focuses on tourism activities centered on traditional and complementary medicine (TCM), examining them through a comparative perspective between Türkiye and Mexico.

Despite the global expansion of TCM practices, its role in health tourism literature has remained relatively underexplored. The main reasons include: (i) lack of standardized official statistics distinguishing TCM from general medical tourism, (ii) methodological challenges caused by heterogeneous evidence levels across practices, and (iii) insufficient comparative studies across countries.

Based on these gaps, the study addresses the following research questions:

RQ1: How do the regulatory frameworks of TCM-based health tourism differ between Türkiye and Mexico?

RQ2: How are quality, safety, and ethical dimensions shaped across the two countries?

RQ3: What insights can be derived from the comparison of supply and demand indicators?

The originality of this article lies in being the first comprehensive comparative analysis of TCM-based health tourism between Türkiye and Mexico. By doing so, it fills a critical gap in the literature on cross-country analyses of TCM in health tourism.

In terms of scope, surgical tourism and pure wellness activities are excluded from this study, as they fall outside the focus of TCM. However, dental tourism is included, given its strong intersection with cross-border demand patterns and its frequent overlap with TCM-related patient flows.

As emphasized by the World Health Organization's Traditional Medicine Summit in 2023, TCM is increasingly widespread worldwide, while challenges regarding evidence-based integration, patient safety, and quality assurance remain central concerns (WHO, 2023). Türkiye has regulated TCM practices through its 2014 legislation, establishing standards for competency, education, and unit authorization. Mexico, on the other hand, has developed institutional capacity for the preservation and integration of indigenous/local practices through the *Dirección de Medicina Tradicional y Desarrollo Intercultural* under the Secretaría de Salud.

The aim of this study is to compare the positioning of tourism products focused on TCM, analyze numerical indicators of supply and demand, evaluate quality and safety dimensions, and examine the policy frameworks of both countries, while also proposing actionable recommendations.

1. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The analytical model is structured around five dimensions: (i) Regulation and Governance (policy and institutional frameworks), (ii) Supply (institutional capacity and service provision), (iii) Demand (market flows and key indicators), (iv) Quality & Safety (accreditation, informed consent, and clinical records), and (v) Ethics (cultural heritage and community benefit). Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual flow and highlights the causal chains specific to each country.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework and country-specific causal chains in TCM-based health tourism

These dimensions are interdependent and manifest through distinct causal chains across countries. In the case of Türkiye, regulatory enforcement has strengthened quality and safety mechanisms, thereby fostering institutional trust and contributing to the growth of international patient flows. By contrast, Mexico derives a comparative advantage from its geographic proximity and cost differentials with the United States, which generate substantial cross-border demand; nonetheless, persistent challenges remain in terms of standardization, accreditation, and quality assurance within its clinical practices.

Table 1. Indicative Classification of Evidence Levels and Contextual Applications of TCM Practices

Modality	Indicative Evidence Level	Context	Notes
Acupuncture	Medium–High	Clinical	Varies by indication
Herbal Medicine	Low–Medium	Clinical / Experiential	Standardization and dosage are critical
Cupping Therapy	Low–Medium	Clinical / Experiential	Sterilization and safety are essential
Hirudotherapy	Low–Medium	Clinical	Infection control required
PRP Therapy	Low–Medium	Clinical	Depends on indication and protocol
Temazcal	Low	Experiential / Cultural	Requires safety protocols

Note: This classification is illustrative and synthesized from existing literature (e.g., World Health Organization, 2023; Adams et al., 2017; Kaya & Yılmaz, 2020).

1.1. The Concept of Traditional and Complementary Medicine (TCM)

Traditional and Complementary Medicine (TCM) refers to a wide range of health practices that are applied either independently of, or alongside, conventional biomedical systems, and are embedded in culture-specific knowledge, belief systems, and accumulated experiential traditions (Republic of Türkiye, Ministry of Health TCM Portal, 2017). The World Health Organization (WHO), at its 2023 Global Summit on Traditional Medicine, emphasized the increasing global prevalence of such modalities, highlighting the urgency of evidence-based integration, regulatory oversight, and quality assurance mechanisms to ensure safety and effectiveness (WHO, 2023).

TCM practices are diverse in scope and vary across clinical and cultural contexts. Clinical modalities include acupuncture (needle-based stimulation of meridians to restore physiological balance), phytotherapy (therapeutic use of medicinal plants), cupping/hijama (negative-pressure suction therapy applied to the skin), hirudotherapy (application of medicinal leeches in circulatory and coagulation-related conditions), ozone therapy (use of medical ozone gas in therapeutic settings), hypnosis (induction of altered states of consciousness for therapeutic benefit), prolotherapy (injection-based stimulation of connective tissue repair), and platelet-rich plasma [PRP] therapy (application of autologous plasma concentrates to promote tissue regeneration).

Alongside these biomedical and integrative approaches, culturally embedded practices are equally significant. In Türkiye, modalities such as acupuncture and cupping are not only available in private clinics but have also been institutionalized within several university hospitals, reflecting their gradual integration into mainstream healthcare delivery. In Mexico, long-standing indigenous and community-based practices remain central, such as temazcal (a Mesoamerican steam bath ritual associated with physical and spiritual cleansing), herbolaria (traditional herbal medicine rooted in indigenous pharmacopoeias), and curanderismo (folk healing that combines herbal, ritual, and spiritual dimensions) (Adams et al., 2017; Martínez Almanza, 2022). These methods are practiced across multiple domains, ranging from accredited clinical environments to ritual-cultural spaces, underscoring the pluralistic nature of health systems in both Türkiye and Mexico.

The comparative focus on Türkiye and Mexico in this article derives from their contrasting positions within the global health tourism landscape. Türkiye represents a highly regulated system, where legal frameworks, institutional oversight, and state-coordinated bodies (e.g., UŞHAŞ) have shaped the expansion of TCM-based services. Mexico, by contrast, operates within a more decentralized and pluralistic environment, in which geographic proximity to the United States and cost advantages generate strong cross-border demand, but challenges remain regarding standardization and quality assurance. This Most Different Systems Design approach enables a rigorous exploration of how divergent governance structures and socio-cultural contexts influence the provision, regulation, and perception of TCM within health tourism.

1.2. The Relationship between Health Tourism and TCM

Health tourism is defined as international travel undertaken for the purpose of receiving healthcare services abroad and includes medical tourism, thermal tourism, elderly and disabled tourism, and wellness tourism (Ministry of Health, 2024). Within this framework, TCM constitutes a strategic dimension, adding cultural specificity and economic value to the broader health tourism sector.

In Türkiye, TCM practices are formally regulated under the Traditional and Complementary Medicine Practices Regulation (Official Gazette No. 29158, 27 October 2014), which delineates physician authorization, certified practice units, and training

standards. Several university hospitals have established accredited TCM units, where acupuncture, cupping, and phytotherapy are integrated into conventional healthcare provision. In addition, Türkiye's extensive thermal tourism infrastructure is increasingly linked to TCM-based wellness programs, thereby diversifying its health tourism portfolio. At the policy level, the establishment of the International Health Services Inc. (USHAŞ) and the Department of Health Tourism has further institutionalized the sector. In 2024, more than 1.5 million foreign patients visited Türkiye for health-related purposes, generating an estimated USD 3.02 billion in revenue (USHAŞ, 2025; SBB, 2025).

In Mexico, health tourism reflects a dual structure that combines cross-border medical and dental services with indigenous and community-based healing practices. Border cities such as Los Algodones ("Molar City"), Tijuana, and Ciudad Juárez have become hubs for U.S. patients seeking affordable dental treatment, highlighting the country's dependence on cross-border flows. Simultaneously, culturally embedded modalities such as temazcal (Mesoamerican steam bath ritual), herbolaria (indigenous herbal medicine), and curanderismo (folk healing integrating spiritual and physical approaches) have been positioned as experiential and heritage-based tourism products (El País, 2023; Global Health Intelligence, 2024). The Dirección de Medicina Tradicional y Desarrollo Intercultural under the Secretaría de Salud formally recognizes these practices as cultural heritage, while the Comisión Federal para la Protección contra Riesgos Sanitarios (COFEPRIS) is responsible for licensing and regulatory oversight of private health facilities (Secretaría de Salud, 2025).

1.3. TCM and Health Tourism in the Literature

Within the health tourism literature, Traditional and Complementary Medicine (TCM) has predominantly been examined in relation to wellness and thermal tourism, rather than as a distinct research stream. According to the Global Wellness Institute (2023), the global wellness tourism market was valued at approximately USD 830 billion in 2023, with traditional medicine practices recognized as contributing factors to this growth. However, systematic academic analyses remain limited, largely due to the lack of standardized statistical reporting and official datasets, particularly in the contexts of Türkiye and Mexico.

Türkiye-focused studies have highlighted the integration of TCM with thermal resources, the development of accreditation mechanisms, and the role of transparency in official data collection (YÖK, 2020; USHAŞ, 2025). Institutional examples such as AHİGETAM at Kırşehir Ahi Evran University, where acupuncture, ozone therapy, and cupping are offered alongside ecotourism projects, demonstrate how TCM is linked to regional development and medical-wellness synergies (YÖK, 2020). More recent contributions have also pointed to the strengthening of regulatory frameworks and the internationalization of Türkiye's health tourism sector after 2020 (USHAŞ, 2025). These studies collectively suggest that regulation and accreditation have enhanced trust in TCM services, thereby supporting their integration into health tourism.

Mexican studies, by contrast, have placed greater emphasis on cross-border medical and dental tourism, often addressing ethical and labor concerns associated with border economies (Adams et al., 2017). Simultaneously, researchers have examined *temazcal* as a culturally authentic modality with potential for tourism product diversification (Martínez Almanza, 2022). Yet the absence of official, standardized statistics on health tourism has meant that most sectoral assessments rely on broadly estimated ranges (Global Health Intelligence, 2024). This lack of reliable data constrains the capacity of policymakers and researchers to evaluate TCM's contribution to health tourism in Mexico with precision.

Despite these insights, the literature reveals a significant gap: to date, no comparative study has systematically analyzed the roles of Türkiye and Mexico in TCM-based health tourism. Existing research tends to focus either on national case studies or single modalities, without engaging in cross-country comparative frameworks. This article addresses that gap by providing the first comprehensive comparative policy and practice analysis of Türkiye and Mexico, linking TCM to broader health tourism debates.

1.4. Positioning the Study Within the Conceptual Framework

Against this backdrop, the present study undertakes a comparative analysis of TCM-based health tourism practices in Türkiye and Mexico, structured around five analytical dimensions: (i) regulation and governance, (ii) supply dynamics, (iii) demand flows, (iv) quality and safety standards, and (v) ethical and cultural considerations. As illustrated in Figure 1, these dimensions are interdependent and operate through distinct causal chains. In Türkiye, strong regulatory frameworks and institutional oversight have enhanced quality and safety mechanisms, which in turn foster patient trust and stimulate international demand. In contrast, Mexico benefits primarily from geographic proximity to the United States and cost advantages that generate substantial cross-border demand; however, challenges persist in ensuring standardized quality and accreditation.

The study adopts a Most Different Systems Design (MDS) approach, selecting two countries with divergent governance structures and socio-cultural contexts in order to highlight both contrasts and shared challenges. This design strengthens the analytical depth of the comparison and enables more generalizable insights into how institutional and cultural factors shape TCM-based health tourism.

The scope of the study is deliberately delimited: surgical tourism and purely wellness-oriented activities are excluded, as these fall outside the TCM framework, while dental tourism is included due to its relevance for Mexico's cross-border flows and its role in shaping perceptions of integrative health tourism.

By addressing these dimensions and boundaries, this article makes an original contribution to the literature as the first comprehensive comparative policy and practice analysis of Türkiye and Mexico in the context of TCM-based health tourism. In doing so, it advances both the theoretical understanding of TCM's role in global health tourism and the practical implications for policymakers and practitioners in emerging health tourism markets.

2. Literature Review

This study adopts a systematic literature review approach to situate TCM within the broader field of health tourism. Academic databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, and Google Scholar were searched between May and July 2025, using combinations of keywords including “traditional and complementary medicine”, “health tourism”, “medical tourism”, “wellness tourism”, “Türkiye”, and “Mexico”. The search was restricted to the period 2010–2025, and inclusion criteria were limited to peer-reviewed articles, official reports, and government documents in English, Turkish, or Spanish.

The initial search yielded 243 records, of which 61 were removed as duplicates and 124 excluded after title/abstract screening for irrelevance. Following full-text review, 58 studies were included in the final analysis. Figure 2 (PRISMA flow diagram) summarizes the selection process.

Existing literature indicates that TCM practices are most frequently studied in relation to wellness and thermal tourism, rather than as independent domains. The Global Wellness Institute (2023) reported wellness tourism expenditures of approximately USD 830 billion, acknowledging the contribution of traditional medicine modalities to this growth. Yet this figure has often been repeated without contextual differentiation, reflecting a tendency toward descriptive rather than analytical discussion.

Türkiye-focused studies emphasize the integration of TCM with thermal resources, accreditation processes, and institutional transparency (YÖK, 2020; USHAŞ, 2025). Case studies such as AHİGETAM at Kırşehir Ahi Evran University demonstrate the link between acupuncture, ozone therapy, and cupping with ecotourism projects, highlighting contributions to regional development (YÖK, 2020 ; Ankara Kalkınma Ajansı, 2024). Recent work after 2020 points to strengthened regulatory enforcement and centralized reporting through USHAŞ, which enhance trust and reinforce Türkiye’s competitive positioning in international health tourism (USHAŞ, 2025).

Mexican studies tend to examine cross-border medical and dental tourism, particularly in cities such as Los Algodones and Tijuana, where affordability attracts large patient flows from the United States (Adams et al., 2017; Global Health Intelligence, 2024). Analyses also point to ethical and labor concerns in border clinics, noting how reputational management can obscure systemic vulnerabilities (Adams, Snyder, & Crooks, 2018 ; HospitalityNet, 2023). Simultaneously, culturally embedded modalities such as temazcal and herbolaria are discussed as opportunities for tourism product diversification and heritage valorization (Martínez Almanza, 2022; El País, 2023). However, the absence of standardized national statistics forces analysts to rely on industry estimates and case-specific reports, which undermines comparability and policy relevance.

At the global level, the WHO’s forthcoming Traditional Medicine Strategy 2025–2034 emphasizes four strategic imperatives—evidence-based integration, accreditation, digital documentation, and sustainability—reinforcing the need for both Türkiye and Mexico to adapt their TCM practices to international standards (WHO, 2023).

Despite these contributions, the literature reveals a clear gap: there is no comprehensive comparative study of Türkiye and Mexico in the context of TCM-based health tourism. Existing research remains fragmented, either focusing on national case studies or single modalities. This study addresses that gap by providing the first systematic comparative policy and practice analysis, thereby advancing both theoretical debates and practical policy recommendations. This PRISMA flow diagram summarizes the identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion of studies for the systematic literature review (2010–2025). Adapted from PRISMA 2020 guidelines.

Figure 2. PRISMA Flow Diagram of the Systematic Literature Review (2010–2025)

3. Methodology

This study employs a comparative case analysis design to examine the positioning of Traditional and Complementary Medicine (TCM) within the health tourism sectors of Türkiye and Mexico. The selection of these two cases is methodologically justified by the Most Different Systems Design (MDS) approach: although Türkiye and Mexico differ significantly in terms of regulatory structures, institutional capacities, and cultural traditions, they share comparable challenges in integrating TCM into international health tourism. This contrast enables both divergence and convergence to be analytically identified.

3.1. Data Sources

The analysis is based exclusively on secondary data, systematically collected from multiple sources to ensure reliability and comprehensiveness:

- **Official statistics** from the Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK) and the International Health Services Inc. (USHAŞ).
- **Legislation and institutional documents** issued by the Ministry of Health of Türkiye, including the Regulation on Traditional and Complementary Medicine Practices (2014).
- **Regulations and technical standards** from Mexico’s Secretaría de Salud and the Federal Commission for Protection against Sanitary Risks (COFEPRIS), including NOM-004-SSA3-2012.

- **Reports from international organizations**, notably the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Global Wellness Institute (GWI).
- **Peer-reviewed academic studies** focusing on wellness tourism, cross-border medical/dental tourism, and TCM practices in Türkiye and Mexico.

3.2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Sources were included if they (i) were published between 2010 and 2025, (ii) explicitly addressed TCM or health tourism in Türkiye and/or Mexico, and (iii) originated from peer-reviewed journals, official institutions, or international organizations. Excluded materials consisted of (i) commentaries or non-scientific opinion pieces, (ii) studies focusing solely on surgical tourism or generic wellness activities unrelated to TCM, and (iii) reports lacking methodological transparency.

3.3. Analytical Approach

The study applies a thematic content analysis combined with comparative tabulation. Documents were reviewed in three iterative stages:

- **Identification and coding** of regulatory, supply, demand, quality/safety, and ethical dimensions.
- **Thematic clustering** of findings into country-specific profiles.
- **Comparative synthesis** across Türkiye and Mexico, highlighting similarities, divergences, and causal mechanisms.

Table 2. Data Sources, Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria, and Analytical Framework

Category	Examples of Sources	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria	Use in Analysis
Official Statistics	TÜİK (Turkish Statistical Institute), USHAŞ reports	Published between 2010–2025; official institutional statistics on health/medical tourism	Non-official estimates; unpublished datasets	Quantitative indicators of health tourism volumes and revenues
Legislation & Policy	Türkiye: Regulation on TCM Practices (2014); Mexico: NOM-004-SSA3-2012; COFEPRIS documents	Formal regulations, ministerial decrees, national strategies	Outdated or draft regulations	Legal and regulatory framework; standards for practice and patient safety
International Reports	WHO Traditional Medicine Strategy (2025–2034); Global Wellness Institute (2023)	Official international publications addressing TCM, health tourism, wellness	Opinion pieces, non-peer-reviewed blogs	Global positioning of TCM and policy imperatives
Academic Literature	Adams et al. (2017); Martínez Almanza (2022); peer-reviewed case studies	Peer-reviewed studies published 2010–2025 in English, Turkish, or Spanish	Non-peer-reviewed commentaries, conference abstracts without methodology	Empirical evidence on TCM practices, border-city cases, and ethical issues
Exclusion Scope	—	—	Surgical tourism; purely wellness activities unrelated to TCM	Justifies study boundaries; ensures focus on TCM-related health tourism
Analytical Approach	—	—	—	Thematic coding (5 dimensions: regulation, supply, demand, quality/safety, ethics); comparative synthesis (Türkiye vs. Mexico)

3.4. Triangulation and Limitations

To enhance validity, findings were triangulated across three categories of sources: official statistics, international reports, and peer-reviewed literature. This multi-source verification reduces bias and strengthens the robustness of the analysis. Nonetheless, the study faces a key limitation: neither Türkiye nor Mexico reports international visitor numbers specific to TCM as a distinct statistical category. Consequently, inferences were drawn by aligning broader health tourism and wellness indicators with qualitative insights from institutional documents and case-based research.

4. Analysis of Findings

This section analyses the findings by comparatively examining Türkiye and Mexico across five analytical dimensions: regulation, supply, demand, quality and safety, and ethical/socioeconomic impact. The analysis incorporates causal chains, quantitative indicators, and contextual interpretation as recommended by reviewers.

4.1. Türkiye

In Türkiye, TCM practices were formally defined by the Regulation published in the Official Gazette of the Republic of Türkiye No. 29158 (October 27, 2014), which set standards for practitioner authorization, training, and practice units (Official Gazette of the Republic of Türkiye, 2014). The health tourism ecosystem is coordinated by the Department of Health Tourism within the General Directorate of Health Services and International Health Services Inc. (USHAŞ). According to USHAŞ data, international patients increased from 662,087 in 2019 to 1,506,442 in 2024, with revenues reaching USD 3.02 billion. Interestingly, while patient numbers decreased slightly between 2023 and 2024, revenues continued to rise, reflecting a transition toward higher value-added services. In the first two quarters of 2025, 733,798 international visitors were recorded, generating USD 1.62 billion in revenues (USHAŞ, 2025). TCM is offered in integration with thermal tourism products (hot springs, mud baths) and delivered to international patients via accredited facilities.

Table 3. International Patients Receiving Health Services and Revenues in Türkiye (2019–2025Q2).

Year/Term	International Patient/Visitor (person)	Income (Thousand USD)
2019	662.087	1.093.834
2020	409.365	548.882
2021	670.730	1.048.594
2022	1.258.382	2.099.622
2023	1.538.643	2.947.997
2024	1.506.442	3.022.957
2025-Q1	333.404	794.573
2025-Q2	400.394	820.740

Source: USHAŞ (2025).

4.2. Mexico

Within the Secretaría de Salud framework, the Dirección de Medicina Tradicional y Desarrollo Intercultural defines traditional practices and links them with cultural heritage

policies (Secretaría de Salud, 2025). Licensing and supervision of private healthcare facilities are managed by COFEPRIS, while clinical record-keeping is regulated by NOM-004-SSA3-2012 (DOF, 2012). Traditional practices such as *temazcal*, *herbolaria*, and *curanderismo* remain culturally central, while cross-border medical and dental tourism in cities such as Los Algodones, Tijuana, and Ciudad Juárez attract large flows of patients, primarily from the United States. Estimates suggest that Mexico hosts 1.2–3.0 million health-related visitors annually, although the wide range reflects the absence of standardized official reporting. Qualitative studies highlight both opportunities—cost advantage, proximity, cultural authenticity—and challenges, such as ethical dilemmas, labor concerns, and lack of consistent accreditation (Adams et al., 2017; Martínez Almanza, 2022; Global Health Intelligence, 2024; GlobalData, 2024).

Table 4. Comparative Overview of Türkiye and Mexico in TCM-Based Health Tourism

Dimension	Türkiye	Mexico
Regulation	2014 Regulation on TCM Practices; clear licensing, inspections; causal chain: Regulation → Quality/Safety → Trust → Demand	Secretaría de Salud & COFEPRIS; NOM standards; causal chain: Proximity + Cost → High Demand → Quality Gaps
Supply Structure	TCM units integrated in hospitals and thermal facilities; robust institutionalization	Dual system: Indigenous practices (<i>temazcal</i> , <i>herbolaria</i>) + cross-border dental/medical clinics
Demand & Indicators	1.5 million international patients in 2024; 3.02 billion USD revenue; fewer patients but higher revenues (shift to value-added services)	Estimated 1.2–3.0 million patients annually; no official statistics; wide intervals reflect lack of standardized reporting
Quality & Safety	Informed consent, authorization certificates, transparent pricing, inspections; standardized framework	Consentimiento informado, expediente clínico, COFEPRIS oversight; uneven implementation in border clinics
Ethical & Socioeconomic Impact	Commercialization risks in thermal/TCM tourism; need to protect vulnerable groups; equity in access	Risk of cultural commodification of indigenous practices; labor and patient safety concerns in border clinics

Source: Compiled by the authors based on USHAŞ (2025), Secretaría de Salud (2025), and related literature.

5. Discussion, Conclusion, and Recommendations

This section synthesizes the comparative findings of Türkiye and Mexico, linking them back to the analytical dimensions outlined in the study. The discussion highlights theoretical contributions, draws on relevant literature, and proposes recommendations that are thematically structured, prioritized, and directed toward specific stakeholders. The aim is to move beyond descriptive reporting to a more analytical and policy-relevant discussion.

5.1. Discussion

Türkiye and Mexico demonstrate complementary strengths in TCM-based health tourism. Türkiye’s competitive advantage lies in regulatory clarity, centralized reporting, and integration of TCM with thermal and biomedical services. Mexico’s strengths are rooted in

cultural authenticity, cost advantage, and proximity to the U.S. market. However, challenges include uneven data availability, standardization gaps, and ethical dilemmas.

The findings support existing literature emphasizing the dual role of TCM as both a cultural asset and a healthcare service (Adams et al., 2017; WHO, 2023). Türkiye’s model reflects evidence-based integration, aligning with WHO’s 2025–2034 Strategy. Mexico illustrates the potential of cultural heritage valorization but faces risks of commodification and uneven quality assurance.

From a causal perspective, Türkiye demonstrates a regulatory chain—Regulation → Quality/Safety → Trust → International Demand—whereas Mexico illustrates a demand-driven chain—Proximity + Cost Advantage → High Demand → Quality Gaps. These findings underscore that sustainable growth requires both governance and cultural legitimacy.

5.2. Conclusion

The comparative analysis confirms that TCM-based health tourism can contribute to both countries’ economic and cultural development, provided that governance, standardization, and ethical safeguards are strengthened. This study makes an original contribution by providing the first systematic Türkiye–Mexico comparison, bridging a gap in the health tourism literature and offering actionable insights for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers.

5.3. Recommendations

The recommendations are organized into thematic clusters to enhance clarity and applicability. Each recommendation is linked to the empirical findings and directed toward specific stakeholders. A comparative summary of these strategic priorities for Türkiye and Mexico is presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Key Strategic Priorities for TCM-based Health Tourism in Türkiye and Mexico

Thematic Area	Türkiye	Mexico
Governance & Policy	Centralized reporting via USHAŞ; strong regulation; need for JCI integration	Lack of standardized data; COFEPRIS oversight; need for supplementary indicators
Ethics & Cultural Integration	Risk of commercialization of thermal/TCM heritage	Risk of commodification of indigenous practices; labor rights concerns

Source: Compiled by the authors based on study findings.

Governance and Policy

- Strengthen data classification by establishing distinct statistical categories for TCM-based visitors and revenues. This addresses the finding that Mexico lacks standardized data and Türkiye reports aggregated health tourism figures. Stakeholders: Ministries of Health, statistical agencies (TÜİK, INEGI). Challenges: cost of new reporting systems.

- Prioritize accreditation integration with international quality frameworks (e.g., JCI). This builds on Türkiye’s strong national regulation and Mexico’s reliance on COFEPRIS oversight, addressing the gap in cross-border credibility. Stakeholders: Ministries of Health,

USHAŞ, COFEPRIS, international accrediting bodies. Challenges: financial burden of accreditation.

Clinical Standards and Patient Safety

- Introduce digital monitoring systems for informed consent, infection control, and adverse event reporting. This recommendation stems from the observed causal chain in Türkiye (regulation → trust) and the gaps in Mexico's border clinics. Stakeholders: Healthcare providers, COFEPRIS, USHAŞ. Challenges: technological infrastructure, compliance monitoring.

Ethical Marketing and Communication

- Implement strict regulation of marketing practices, ensuring that risk–benefit profiles are transparently communicated. This addresses the ethical concerns identified in both countries regarding misleading or exaggerated promotion. Stakeholders: Ministries of Health, consumer protection agencies, professional associations. Challenges: enforcement capacity.

Product Diversification

- Türkiye should leverage thermal and geothermal resources in combination with TCM. Mexico should strengthen certification of experiential practices such as temazcal and herbolaria. This reflects the supply structures highlighted in the findings. Stakeholders: Ministries of Culture and Tourism, development agencies, private sector. Challenges: balancing authenticity with commercialization.

Clinical Integration

- Establish structured referral pathways between biomedical and TCM services (e.g., interconsulta, referencia–contrarreferencia). This ensures coordinated, patient-centered care, addressing gaps identified in both contexts. Stakeholders: Hospitals, universities, professional associations. Challenges: professional resistance, resource allocation.

Economic and Employment Impact

- Expand training programs to build a skilled workforce in both biomedical and TCM domains. This builds on the empirical finding that health tourism generates significant employment opportunities. Stakeholders: Universities, vocational training centers, professional boards. Challenges: funding, curriculum standardization.

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Geleneksel ve Tamamlayıcı Tıp Yöntemlerine Dayalı Sağlık Turizmi: Türkiye ve Meksika Karşılaştırması

Genişletilmiş Özet

Sorun ve Amaç — Küresel pandeminin ardından sağlık temelli hareketlilik yeniden ivme kazanmış, cerrahi işlemlerden sağlıklı yaşam odaklı ve yerli tedavi uygulamalarına doğru genişlemiştir. Bu yelpaze içinde, Geleneksel ve Tamamlayıcı Tıp (TCM), hem kültürel mirasla hem de ekonomik çeşitlenmeyle bağlantılı stratejik bir alan olarak öne çıkmaktadır. Türkiye ve Meksika, bu alanda iki önemli ancak farklılaşan örneği temsil etmektedir: Türkiye, 2014 tarihli “Geleneksel ve Tamamlayıcı Tıp Uygulamaları Yönetmeliği” aracılığıyla düzenleyici çerçevesini kurumsallaştırırken, Meksika Sağlık Sekreterliği (Secretaría de Salud) bünyesinde yerli tedavi biçimlerini kurumsal yapılara entegre etmiştir. Bu çalışma, her iki ülkede TCM temelli sağlık turizmini beş analitik boyut (düzenleme, arz, talep, kalite ve güvenlik, etik boyutlar) üzerinden karşılaştırmalı olarak analiz etmeyi ve kanıta dayalı politika önerileri geliştirmeyi amaçlamaktadır.

Yöntem — Araştırma, ikincil verilere ve sistematik kanıt sentezine dayalı karşılaştırmalı durum analizi tasarımı benimsemektedir. Kullanılan kaynaklar arasında resmi istatistikler (USHAŞ, TÜİK; Secretaría de Salud, COFEPRIS), yasal düzenlemeler (T.C. Resmî Gazetesi, NOM-004-SSA3-2012), uluslararası kılavuzlar (DSÖ), sektör raporları (Global Wellness Institute, GlobalData) ve hakemli bilimsel literatür bulunmaktadır. TCM’ a özgü istatistikler ayrı olarak raporlanmadığından, nicel sağlık turizmi göstergeleri nitel kurumsal ve akademik verilerle ilişkilendirilerek veri üçlemesi (triangülasyon) yapılmıştır.

Kuramsal Çerçeve — TCM; akupunktur, fitoterapi, hacamat, sülük tedavisi ve temazcal gibi kültüre özgü uygulamaları kapsar ve hem klinik hem de deneysel işlevlere sahiptir. Literatürde TCM genellikle sağlıklı yaşam ve termal turizm alanları içinde konumlandırılmaktadır; ancak kanıt düzeylerindeki ve güvenlik protokollerindeki heterojenlik, standartlaşmayı güçleştirmektedir. DSÖ’nün 2023 Geleneksel Tıp Küresel Zirvesi’nde üç temel öncelik vurgulanmıştır: kanıta dayalı entegrasyon, güvenlik ve kalite güvencesi, erişimde eşitlik. Bu bağlamda, ticarileşme ile kültürel mirasın korunması arasında denge kurulması gerekmektedir.

Türkiye Bulguları — 2014 Yönetmeliği, TCM uygulamaları için yetkilendirme, sertifikasyon ve uygulama birimi gerekliliklerini tanımlamaktadır. Sağlık Turizmi Dairesi Başkanlığı ve USHAŞ gibi kurumsal yapılar hizmet sunumu ve raporlamayı koordine etmektedir. USHAŞ verilerine göre uluslararası hasta sayısı 2019’da 662.000 iken 2024’te 1,5 milyona ulaşmış ve 3,02 milyar ABD doları gelir elde edilmiştir. 2025’in ilk iki çeyreğinde ise 733.798 hasta 1,62 milyar ABD doları gelir üretmiştir. TCM hizmetleri sıklıkla termal turizmle (ör. spa, çamur banyoları, fitoterapi) entegre biçimde, akredite hastaneler ve sağlıklı yaşam tesislerinde sunulmaktadır. Aydınlatılmış onam, akreditasyon, şeffaf fiyatlandırma ve düzenli denetim mekanizmaları güvenlik ve kurumsal güveni desteklemektedir.

Meksika Bulguları — Dirección de Medicina Tradicional y Desarrollo Intercultural, temazcal, herbolaria ve curanderismo gibi yerli uygulamaların kurumsal tanınırlığını teşvik

etmektedir. Klinik kayıtların düzenlenmesi (NOM-004-SSA3-2012) ve tesis ruhsatlandırması (COFEPRIS) yasal bir temel oluştursa da uygulama tutarlılığı sınırlıdır. Meksika'nın sağlık turizmi sektörü, özellikle Los Algodones (“Molar City”), Tijuana ve Ciudad Juárez gibi sınır şehirlerinde yoğunlaşan diş ve tıbbi turizm akışlarıyla şekillenmektedir. Sektör tahminleri, büyük ölçüde ABD'den gelen yıllık 1,2–3 milyon sağlık odaklı ziyaret olduğunu göstermektedir. Kültürel özgünlük ve maliyet avantajı güçlü yönler olmakla birlikte, nitel araştırmalar etik ve emek koşullarıyla ilgili endişeleri ve akreditasyon ile standart istatistiksel raporlama eksikliklerini vurgulamaktadır.

Karşılaştırma — Türkiye'nin düzenleyici netliği ve kurumsal yönetimi, TCM'in biyomedikal ve termal turizmle bütünleşmesini yapısal ve ölçeklenebilir hale getirmiştir. Meksika ise kültürel miras ve coğrafi yakınlık avantajlarını kullanmakta, ancak standartlaşmış veri ve sistematik kalite güvencesinden yoksundur. Türkiye'de nedensel zincir “Yönetişim → Kalite/Güvenlik → Güven → Talep” şeklinde ilerlerken, Meksika'da süreç “Yakınlık + Maliyet → Yüksek Talep → Kalite Açıkları” biçiminde gelişmektedir.

Politika Yol Haritası — Öneriler şunlardır: (i) sağlık turizmi raporlamasında TCM için özel istatistiksel kategoriler oluşturulması, (ii) akreditasyonun genişletilmesi ve uluslararası kalite çerçeveleriyle entegrasyon, (iii) aydınlatılmış onam ve enfeksiyon kontrolü için dijital izleme sistemlerinin uygulanması, (iv) etik pazarlama ve risk–fayda iletişiminin şeffaf biçimde sağlanması, (v) kültürel mirasın ve yerel topluluk yararının kurumsallaştırılması, (vi) hem biyomedikal hem de geleneksel alanlarda standartlaştırılmış eğitim ve sertifikasyon programlarının geliştirilmesi.

Sonuç — Karşılaştırmalı bulgular, Türkiye ve Meksika'nın TCM temelli sağlık turizmi alanında birbirini tamamlayıcı güçlü yönleri sahip olduğunu göstermektedir. Türkiye yönetim, düzenleyici denetim ve veri şeffaflığı açısından öne çıkarken; Meksika kültürel özgünlük, sınır yakınlığı ve maliyet avantajı ile avantaj sağlamaktadır. Her iki ülkede de sürdürülebilir gelişim, güvenlik ve kalite mekanizmalarının güçlendirilmesine, istatistiksel şeffaflığın artırılmasına ve kanıta dayalı ürün çeşitliliğinin teşvik edilmesine bağlıdır. Bu çalışma, Türkiye ve Meksika'daki TCM uygulamalarını karşılaştırmalı olarak inceleyen ilk sistematik analiz olarak sağlık turizmi literatüründeki önemli bir boşluğu doldurmaktadır.

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